

Influence of Resources on Employee Job Performance in Hospitality Industry in Ilorin South, Ilorin Kwara State

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Abstract

Resources are vital to the work environment and have directly affected the human performance, contribution to organization goals and subtly changed interpersonal interactions and thus productivity. This study examined the influence of resources on employee job performance in hospitality industry in Ilorin South, Ilorin Kwara State. Five research objectives were raised, and they translated to research questions, three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised both junior and senior staff of the hospitality industry in Ilorin South Local Government Area numbering five hundred and four (504). 29.7% of the total population was used to arrive at a total number of (150) employee that constituted the study sample. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive (frequency, percentages, mean and standard deviation), also inferential statistics such Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The study revealed that training motivates employees to be more committed towards organizational goals (97.9%), training helps improve overall required skills (80.7%) in hospitality industry, adequate rest periods (74.7%), reward system (74.7%), provision of necessary material resources (70%) and accomplishment of tasks with limited human resource (72%) have positive influence on their job performance. The result also revealed that being a particular gender (72%) does not have influence on job performance, it also revealed that years of working experience (66%) determine the utilization of resources, knowledge on utilization of resources (77.7%), and experience (74.7%) play significant roles in job performance of employees. The result also revealed that there is significant relationship between availability of adequate human and materials resources and employees job performance. ($p=0.000$). The study concludes that resources influence the job performance of hospitality staff. Based on the findings, the study recommends that hospitality industry should provide adequate inputs and measures for employees to promote high level of job performance.

Keywords: Resources, Employees, Organization, Hospitality Industry, Job Performance

Introduction

An organization's success mostly depends on its employee's performance. Good employee's performance may be influenced through adequate resources and thereby increase the chance of an organization success in the competitive environment. Aim of every organization is to satisfy its customers to keep them loyal and consequently earn more profit so first they must provide and require prerequisites to meet the needs and demands of their

employees. Hospitality is essentially a relationship based on hosts and guests' and it is the host-guest relationship that is the key distinguishing characteristic of the hospitality industry from which several other dimensions emerge. The concept of hospitality is reception and entertainment of guests or visitors with generosity and good will. The most vital aspect of it refers to warm welcome, reception and amiability. The warmth reception, translate to providing a

pleasant atmosphere by means of its available resources and activities. Hospitality is all about given personal care to people who are away from their homes. Hospitality industry is a wide group of fields within the service industry which includes lodging, event planning, theme parks, transportation, cruise line, travelling and additional field within the tourism industry.

Resources are anything that can be used to accomplish something or an asset for achieving a goal. (Anyakoha, 2015) It plays a vital role in employee's job performance. Human and nonhuman resources are what are needed for the successful running of a Hospitality industry. Human resources like Knowledge, Skills, Energy, and Time are those resources that exist within each individual at all times. Non-human resources like money, building, equipment, tools, transport service, exist outside an individual but can however be owned, controlled and used by individuals, families and businesses (Anyakoha, 2015). Resources are assets, tools, talents and possessions which people use to solve their everyday problems in life. Training is defined as "the process of developing a staff member's knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to perform tasks required for a position" (Hayes & Ninemeier, 2009). Training and development can influence organizational performance also in the hospitality industry (Aksu, 2005; Boella & Goss-Turner, 2012; Joshi & Naik, 2018). The fundamental aim of training is to help an organization to achieve its goal by adding value to its key resources, employees (Ansah & Rita, 2019). Today the exceptionally competitive business area, in which business operates, demands a skillful workforce in order to stay a compelling actor in the centered session of the clientele. One of the essential hindrances which occur in the workplace is the unlucky deficiency of training and growth. (Habib & Hossain, 2016).

Human resource is the most important asset in any organization. It is necessary for organizations to manage their employees effectively and efficiently. This resource controls the non-human resource. It, thus,

requires the considerable attention of the management so that employees can work up to their full potential (Ahmad & Schroeder, 2003). Human resources are personal characteristics people possess and can be used to achieve their desired goals.

Non-Human resources exist outside an individual but can be used and possessed by everyone. The work environment comprises the totality of forces, actions and other influential factors that are currently and potentially contending with the employee's performance and productivity. It shows the interrelationships that exist within the employees in person and their working environment (O'Neill, 2010).

An employee is a person who works for another in return for financial or other dispensation. (Purcell, Kinnie & Hutchinson 2003). Employee is an individual who was hired by an employer to do a specific job. The employee is hired by the employer after an application and interview process results in his or her selection as an employee. Job performance is a way to assess whether a person performs his or her job well or properly. Job performance is an activity in which a person can execute a task allotted to him/her successfully, subject to the normal problems of reasonable utilization of available resources. It consists of the observable behaviors that people do in their jobs that are relevant to the goals of the organizations (Campbell, McHenry, & Wise, 1990). It is the responsibility of the company managers to ensure that the organizations strive to and thus achieve high performance levels. This therefore implies that managers must set the desired levels of performance for any periods in question. This can be done by setting goals and standards against which individual performance can be measured. Every company must provide support for their employees regarding their gender and individual needs to be competitive and long-lasting in the market. Working experience is also a key factor in any organization, Educated and experienced people in any business are responsible for creating organizational wealth.

Statement of the Problem

Globally, the hospitality industry is acknowledged to be of significance to the economic growth of any nation. However, in most developing countries, Nigeria inclusive there are still setbacks in the industry in the respect of lack of adequate resources and inability of employees to make use of the available resources properly. These industries still underperform in relation to resources development and training and do not have the capability to operate effectively and efficiently. Also, meagre staff remuneration, poor motivation in terms of compensation and inadequate recognition of staff for hard work among other poor working conditions have been linked with the hotel industry in Ilorin metropolis (Adediran, 2019; Adediran&Sule, 2019). As a result, might hinder the hospitality business that is planned to serve as the economic boost of the state. The number of hospitality industry is increasing considerably, and the country investment rates are rising substantially. This contributes towards a higher level of competition in the hospitality industry. The hotels and catering organizations underperform, still deliver inadequate services, and provide limited facilities compared to similar businesses; this can have a negative impact on the industry. This study will contribute to minimizing this gap and thereby establish the basis to which the proper utilization of resources by employees would influence job performance in hospitality industry in Ilorin South, Kwara State.

Research Question

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the importance of training employees for effective job performance in the hospitality industry in Ilorin South, Kwara State?
2. What is the perception of employees on organization's human and material resources to job performance in the hospitality industry in Ilorin South, Kwara State?
3. What is the influence of gender on employee's job performance in the hospitality industry in Ilorin South, Kwara State?
4. What is the relationship between employee's resource utilization and years of working experience in the hospitality industry in Ilorin South, Kwara State?

Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant influence between human and material resources and employee's job performance.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey design. It helps in collecting views, facts, and opinion on what exists. A descriptive survey design was preferred for this study because information was gathered from individuals who formed a representative sample of the population. After collation and analysis of the results, the findings can be generalized to the significant larger population of the study.

Population of the Study

The target population of the study comprised all staff of the Hotels in Ilorin South LGA Ilorin Kwara State. The total population is five hundred and four (504)

Sample Size and Sampling Technique:

simple random sampling was used to select thirty percent (30%) of the respondents to give a sample size of one hundred and fifty (150) respondents.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size of the Study

S/N	Hotel	Population	Random selection of hotels (30%)
1	E - phonix	70	21
2	Princess luxury	86	26
3	Water view	35	11
4	Rehoboth	30	9
5	Bekadims	50	15
6	Royalton Palace	60	18
7	Fairyland	40	12
8	Purple Hills	48	14
9	De Peace	45	12
10	Suitoria	40	12
Total		504	150

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled, "Job performance Questionnaire" (JPQ). The instrument contains twenty-eight (28) items on a four (4) point rating scale of Strongly Disagree (SD-1), Disagree (D-2), Agree (A-3), Strongly Agree (SA-4)

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics used include frequencies, percentages and mean and inferential statistics Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for mean score was based on the four-point rating scale of 2.50 by which a mean rating of an item by the respondents equal to or above 2.50 was taken as agreed while less than 2.50 was taken as disagreed.

Results and Discussions

The socio demographic information of the respondents revealed that 85 (56.7%) were males, while 65 (43.3%) were female, 105 (70%) were between age 21 and 30 years, 87 (58%) have between 0 and 5 years working experience

Analysis of the Research Questions

Table 2 presents the mean score and remarks on importance of training employees for effective Job performance in the hospitality industry. From the table, nine of the items were agreed; this is because they have a mean score that are above the mid-mean score of 2.50, this implies that majority of the respondents believed that training of the employees has impact on job performance. That is, training helps to improve overall required skills ($\bar{x}$ = 3.54), also training motivates employees to be more committed towards organizational goals (= 3.66), training helps in improving relation with clients (= 3.63), training helps the organization to meet and exceed their expectations (= 2.55), training also aids in organizational developments (= 3.53), while one of the items disagreed; this is because they have a mean score that are below the mid-mean score of 2.50, That is, training has improved general disciplinary level of employees (= 2.48). This is a proof that organization of training for the employees will contribute to effective job performance.

Table 2: Importance of Training Employees for Effective Job Performance in the Hospitality Industry

N.	Items	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Remark
1.	Training helps improve overall required skills	4 (2.7)	4 (2.7)	66 (44.0)	76 (36.7)	3.54	Agreed
2.	Training motivates employees to be more committed towards organizational goals		3 2.0	65 43.3	82 54.6	3.66	Agreed
3.	Training helps in improving relation with clients	4 2.7	4 2.7	66 44.0	76 50.7	3.63	Agreed
4.	Training helps the organization to meet and exceed their expectations	16 10.7	36 24.0	56 37.3	42 28.0	2.55	Agreed
5.	Training also aids in organizational developments		50 33.3	40 36.7	60 40.0	3.53	Agreed
6.	Training has improved general disciplinary level of employees	16 10.7	42 28.0	56 37.3	36 24.0	2.48	Disagreed
7.	Training has helped attain team work and group goals	16 10.7	12 8.0	33 22.0	89 59.3	3.03	Agreed
8.	Training has helped in developing supervisory roles	28 18.7	33 22.0	37 24.7	60 40.0	2.51	Agreed
9.	Training has helped in developing leadership skills	12 8.0	12 8.0	60 40.0	66 44.0	2.62	Agreed
10.	Training helps to set organizational performance goals	3 2.0	4 2.7	49 32.7	94 62.7	3.91	Agreed

Table 3 presents the mean score and remarks on the perception of employees on organization contribution of resources. From the table, five of the items were agreed; this is because they have a mean score that are above the mid-mean score of 2.50, this implies that some respondents believed that organization contribution of resources has impact on job performance. That is, rest period/break would influence their job performance ($\bar{x}$ = 2.71), also unwillingness to perform a task affect job performance (= 2.55), reward system influence job performance (= 2.71), provision of necessary material resources (= 2.55) while four of the items were disagreed;

this is because they have a mean score that are below the mid-mean score of 2.50, That is, high paid workers do not perform job better than low paid workers (= 2.37), structural layout of the premises do not ease their job performance (= 2.36), and their organization do not provide them with training opportunities to extend their skills and abilities and job cannot be performed adequately because of lack of resources (= 2.38). This is a proof that organization contribution of resources is important to employee's job performance.

Table 3: Mean Rating on The Perception Of Employees On Human And Material Resources To Job Performance

S/N	Statements	SD	D	A	SA	Mean score	Remarks
1	Rest period/break influences job performance	10 (6.7)	28 (18.7)	57 (38.0)	55 (36.7)	2.71	Agreed
2	High paid workers perform jobs better than low paid workers	29 (19.3)	36 (24.0)	43 (28.7)	42 (28.0)	2.37	Disagreed
3	Structural layout of the premises eases job performance	25 (16.6)	19 (12.7)	68 (45.3)	35 (23.3)	2.36	Disagreed
4	Worker attitude and social skills affect job performance	30 (20.0)	15 (10.0)	65 (43.3)	40 (26.7)	2.55	Agreed
5	My organization has provided me training opportunities enabling me to extend my skills and abilities	39 (26.0)	17 (11.3)	47 (31.3)	47 (31.3)	2.38	Disagreed
6.	Organization provision of necessary resource do have great impact on my performance	15 (10.0)	30 (20.0)	65 (43.3)	40 (26.7)	2.55	Agreed
7.	Jobs can be well performed without provision of adequate material resources	47 (31.3)	17 (11.3)	39 (26.0)	47 (31.3)	2.38	Disagreed
8.	Reward systems influence job performance	10 (6.7)	28 (18.7)	57 (38.0)	55 (36.7)	2.71	Agreed
9.	I accomplish my task within the limited available human resource	28 (18.7)	14 (8.3)	66 (44.0)	42 (28.0)	2.57	Agreed

Table 4 shows influence of gender on the performance of employees in hospitality industry. Respondents agreed to items 1,4 and 5 while disagreed to items 2 and 3. This

implies that respondent's gender do not really have influence on job performance of the respondents.

Table 4: Mean Rating of Respondents on Influence of Gender on Employee job performance

S/N	Statements	SD	D	A	SA	Mean score	Remarks
1	I can perform my duties with ease without much fatigue when working with same gender co-worker	20 (13.3)	17 (11.3)	58 (38.7)	56 (36.7)	2.60	Agreed
2	I meet my work hour schedule when working with same gender	37 (24.4)	12 (8.0)	62 (41.3)	39 (26.0)	2.41	Disagreed
3	I get bored/frustrated over repetitive task because of my gender	37 (24.7)	36 (24.0)	50 (33.3)	27 (18.0)	2.08	Disagreed
4	Irrespective of my gender I can accomplish my task well	28 (18.7)	14 (8.3)	66 (44.0)	42 (28.0)	2.57	Agreed
5	As a result of gender am assigned certain task	22 (14.7)	18 (12.0)	62 (41.3)	48 (32.0)	2.72	Agreed

Table 5 shows the relationship between employee's utilization of resources and years of working experience. Respondents agreed to items 2 and 3 and disagreed to 1 and 4.

The respondents view on this showed that years of working experience has great influence on utilization of resources among respondents.

Table 5: Mean Rating of Respondents on Relationship Between Employee's Utilization of Resources and Years of Working Experience

S/N	Statements	SD (1)	D (2)	A(3)	SA(4)	Mean score	Remarks
1	Years of experience do not determine utilization of resources	26 (17.3)	25 (16.6)	69 (46.0)	30 (20.0)	2.46	Disagreed
2	Knowledge on utilization of resources increases job performance	28 (18.7)	5 (3.4)	65 (43.3)	52 (34.7)	2.73	Agreed
3	Experience is more important in increasing job performance	27 (18.0)	8 (5.3)	63 (42.0)	52 (34.7)	2.72	Agreed
4	Adequate resources not year of experience increases job performance	62 (41.3)	16 (10.7)	40 (26.7)	32 (21.3)	2.26	Disagreed

Test of Hypothesis

Table 6 shows an r value of .291** and a P value of .000 Testing at an alpha level of 0.05, the p value is less than the alpha level. ($p < 0.05$) therefore, the null hypothesis which states that 'There is no significant relationship between availability of adequate

human and material resources and employee's job performance is rejected. Consequently, there is significant relationship between availability of adequate human and material resources and employee's job performance.

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics on relationship between availability of adequate human and material resources and employee's job performance

Variables	N	X	SD	R	Sig.p(2tailed)	Remark
Availability of adequate resource	150	13.13	4.94	.291**	.000	S
Level of Job Performance		19.92	.55			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Discussion of the findings

Findings from research question 1 revealed the influence of training on the employee's work performance in the organization. Majority of them believed that training has a positive influence on their work performed in the organization. This is in line with Plessis, Douangphichit, Dodd (2016) which says training of employees played a significant role in job performance in hospitality industry.

Finding of research question 2 revealed that staff in hospitality industry performs task based on availability of both human and materials resources, also working environment, its features and organization contribution to employee necessities (such as rest period/ breaks, rewarding system, good structural layout) influence job performance. This finding agrees with Williams and O'Reilly (2001) who revealed that short-term outcomes of job stress have both physiological and behavioral effects leading to poor job performance. In a study conducted by Siron and Tasripan (2012), it was reported that to increase the performance of employees and managers, the Libyan industrial companies must handle the issues of workplace stress effectively. Additional formulation is that Ainsworth, Smith, and Millership, (2008) have pointed out three elements that must be conducive for employee welfare during work: the physical environment -tools and the

workplace physical conditions; the human environment- group factors such as compatibility, team cohesiveness and leadership factors; the organization- clarity of structure, systems, communication of priorities, emphasis and the workplace culture.

Finding of research question 3 revealed that individual gender does not affect job performance, and that irrespective of the gender, employee perform job effectively when working with co-workers. This agrees with (Wang, Tsai, Tsai, 2014) in the recent competitive environment, every company must provide support for employees for workers to be competitive and long-lasting in the market.

Finding of research question 4 revealed that there is a relationship between utilization of resources and years of working experience in relation to job performance and that new staff will be moderately effective if the required resource is readily available to perform job. This finding agrees with (Ahmadi., Jalilian, Salamzadeh, Saeidpour, & Daraei, 2012), that the skills and knowledge gained from the previous work experience improve current productivity, the beliefs of self-efficacy, the response time when faced with work challenges, lead to the overall improvement of the job performance. It also agrees with study of (Bello & Bello, 2021) that openness

to experience is positively related to employees' job performance.

The result of the hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between availability of human and material resources and employee job performance. This shows that employee will be more productive when resources are adequately available regardless of the gender or years of experience, this finding agrees with Wright and Geroy (2001) which note that employee competency change through availability of effective resource in carrying out tasks. Stoner, Freeman & Gilbert (1995) revealed that productivity is expressed as a ratio of output to that of input. It is a measure of how the individual, organization and industry converts input resources into goods and services and it is also a measure of how much output is produced per unit of resources employed.

The hospitality industry should provide more training that is necessary for employees to improve and increase their ability and better their performance at work. The industry should also understand that apart from self-actualization needs, self-esteems need, money is the most important factor that drives hotel employees to work hard and should consider the factors to increase employees' job satisfaction which brings about an increase in employee commitment to the organization and results in their organizational performance and satisfaction. The industry should reconsider and develop fair compensation policies for all employees as it is more likely to result in employee satisfaction which leads to the increase of employees' work performance, higher level of employee commitment and higher retention levels. The industry should also work on their organizational working environment, rewards system, flexible work arrangements, and their organizational promotion systems to ensure that there is a high level of employee motivation which results in an increase of employee work performance, and an improvement of organizational productivity.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It can be concluded from the finding that

resource is vital in hospitality industry and resource has significant influence on employee job performance. For a company to grow and survive it must set high value on resource, since resource has positive influence on employee job performance and employee are the cover stone of all industry. Also, adequate resources are needed for effective job performance. For a company to survive her central focus should be the employee and most set efficient strategic goals. To have effective employee and efficient goals organization should fund more on resource since employee who are provided with proper resource (human and nonhuman) tend to keep their jobs longer than those who do not have adequate resource. The time and energy which are human resources utilized by individual would be minimized in accomplishing daily task thereby reducing work stress and increasing productivity

Based on the finding the following hospitality recommendations are made:

1. Hospitality industry should provide adequate inputs and measures for employees to promote high level of job performance.
2. Organizations should work on motivation and compensation of staff such including rest periods, staff training and bonuses to encourage positive job performance.
3. The training programs must be viewed as one of the key operational issues if the hotels want to make head ways in the market or in the industry.
4. Management should treat their employees well by improving on provision of conducive organization environment, job related resources and structure

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